

Parameter Estimation of 2R-1C Circuit Using Embedded Hardware and Measured Impedance Modulus*

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2R-1C equivalent circuit is widely used in electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), such as modelling of lithium-ion batteries, bioimpedance analysis and water quality monitoring. It allows for an analysis of the basic electrical behavior of electrochemical systems and understanding of the underlying principles. However, the reported parameter estimation methods are usually deployed on the PC-based processing units that limit *in-situ* and unsupervised applications, where estimation results are free from user inputs. This paper presents a novel methodology for extracting the values of 2R-1C equivalent circuit by solely utilizing the measured impedance modulus. Unlike iterative and PC-based estimation methods, this approach eliminates user inputs in terms of a need for an initial guess, addressing a significant drawback of those approaches. The proposed work was validated by simulated and experimentally obtained impedance. Moreover, details of deployment on the PC-based and embedded hardware were also reported. The utilization of embedded hardware platform (Mega2560) enables an efficient processing of EIS data (80 milliseconds for 100 datapoints) by creating opportunities for *in-situ* parameter extraction of equivalent electrical circuits.

Keywords: Algorithms; embedded hardware platforms; electrical impedance spectroscopy; *in-situ* parameter extraction; 2R-1C equivalent circuit.

1. Introduction

Efficient processing of Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) data with embedded hardware platforms opens new avenues for wider use of equivalent

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electrical circuits in electrochemical analysis with parameter estimation at the measurement spot.¹ Topology of equivalent electrical circuits (models) is usually chosen based on the four main rules: (1) underlying physical and electrochemical processes, (2) small error between a measured impedance and the impedance of the equivalent electrical circuit, (3) high level of correlation between the changes in analyzed process and changes in values of circuit elements, and (4) circuit complexity should be optimized to ensure reliable parameter estimation with available processing units. Equivalent electrical circuits, such as Randles circuit,² also known as 2R-1C circuit (or R - RC circuit), are widely used to model and analyze the behavior of electrochemical systems (charge transfer reactions, diffusion processes, and double-layer capacitance, *etc.*). By fitting the experimental impedance data to the Randles circuit model, it is possible to determine the correlation among the model parameters and their physical interpretation with electrode processes, such as the presence of degradation or aging effects of batteries, fuel cells, sensors, and corrosion protection systems.^{3,4}

Embedded electronics can play a crucial role in parameter estimation of the equivalent electrical circuits. By utilizing the embedded hardware platforms, efficient data processing becomes possible using techniques like EIS, allowing for *in-situ* parameter extraction. Integration of the embedded electronics enables real-time data acquisition, processing, and analysis, enhancing the accuracy and speed of parameter estimation for the equivalent electrical circuits.

This paper presents an innovative technique for extracting parameters of the 2R-1C circuit. Main characteristic of the proposed estimation method is utilization of the embedded hardware platforms, enabling an efficient processing of EIS data. Proposed methodology solely relies on the measured impedance modulus, eliminating the need for iterative or PC-based estimation methods that typically require an initial guess from the user. By addressing this significant drawback, the proposed approach streamlines the parameter extraction process, which in turn creates opportunities for *in-situ* parameter extraction of the equivalent electrical circuits.

2. Related Works and Research Gap

In addition to the PC-based hardware configurations and commercial software packages,⁵ several methods have been reported as approaches for reliable EIS processing. For example, least squares fitting,^{6,7} nonlinear regression,⁸ genetic algorithms,^{9–13} non-iterative approaches,^{14–16} grey-box identification approach,¹⁷ time-domain parameter estimation,¹⁸ and constrained optimization methods, such as Bee colony algorithm,¹⁹ whale optimization algorithm,²⁰ and multi-objective enhanced genetic algorithm.²¹

The estimation accuracy of least squares fitting method is very sensitive to initial guesses provided to the fitting algorithm. Moreover, convergence to the local minima is very common and it can lead to inaccurate parameter estimates.

Similarly, nonlinear regression algorithms may encounter convergence issues due to sensitivity to the initial values quality. Choosing appropriate initial guesses can be challenging, especially when there is limited prior knowledge about the system.

On the other hand, genetic algorithms can be computationally intensive, requiring significant computational resources and time.

The development of the non-iterative method for parameter estimation of 2R-1C equivalent circuit was the focus of our three previous works.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ In these works, we processed complex impedance, which means that measurements of impedance modulus and phase angle were required. In this work, we propose a method with no need for phase angle measurement. Therefore, hardware with reduced complexity is applicable since phase detector is not required. Moreover, the estimation method presented in this work requires lower memory and processing resources, because only one array of data is needed (impedance modulus), instead of two (impedance modulus and phase angle, or resistance and reactance).

Grey-box identification approach necessitates repetitive estimation of covariance and numerical minimization techniques, which are not well suited for real-time parameter estimation conducted *in-situ*.

The main drawback of time domain-based estimation procedures is their requirement for predefining the duration of the square pulse and the value of the reference resistor based on known nominal parameter values. This can lead to significant errors when those parameters are unknown, as is often the case in electrochemical analysis. Another important limitation of time-domain estimation procedures is their impossibility to compare measured and estimated values, unless the true values of circuit parameters are already known.

Therefore, the main goal of this paper is to fill the research gap in developing an estimation method that does not require initial values for the first iteration, or phase angle measurement, that reduces hardware complexity, and minimizes memory and processing resources.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. The proposed method

The 2R-1C circuit (Fig. 1) is composed of series connection of R_1 resistor with the parallel connection of resistor R_2 and capacitor C_2 . Angular frequency [ω (rad/s)] dependence of impedance modulus of such circuit is of particular interest in this paper:

$$Z(\omega) = \frac{\sqrt{(R_1(1 + (\omega R_2 C_2)^2) + R_2)^2 + (\omega R_2^2 C_2)^2}}{1 + (\omega R_2 C_2)^2}. \quad (1)$$

The frequency, denoted as f (Hz), is linked to the angular frequency through the relationship: $\omega = 2\pi f$.

Fig. 1. The proposed method for EIS data processing with the embedded hardware.

The proposed estimation method is based on the processing of only impedance modulus that is measured at N points in the given frequency range, as it is shown in Fig. 1.

Firstly, measured values of Z were squared to calculate Z_s .

$$Z_s = Z^2 = \frac{(R_1(1 + (\omega R_2 C_2)^2) + R_2)^2 + (\omega R_2^2 C_2)^2}{(1 + \omega^2 R_1^2 R_2^2 C_2^2)^2}. \quad (2)$$

This was done to achieve equations with lower complexity in the further estimated steps.

After that, the first derivative of Z_s , labelled as dZ_s in Eq. (3), was computed by employing a numerical approximation known as the central difference method (Eq. (4)):

$$dZ_s = \frac{\partial Z_s}{\partial \omega} = \frac{-2C_2^2 R_2^3 \omega (R_2 + 2R_1)}{(1 + \omega^2 R_1^2 R_2^2 C_2^2)^2}, \quad (3)$$

$$dZ_s(\omega_i) = \frac{Z_s(\omega_{i+1}) - Z_s(\omega_{i-1})}{\omega_{i+1} - \omega_{i-1}}, \quad (4)$$

where i represents integer ranging from 2 to $N - 1$. Even though the accuracy of numerical approximation of the first derivative is subject to the influence of choosing the method (backward, central, or forward), step size, and numerical precision of data, these limitations are usually more visible in cases of higher-order derivatives with large number of variables. On the other hand, numerical approximation methods allow for the calculation of derivatives for functions that may not be directly measured with reasonable execution time (as in the case of electrochemical impedance). This is very important in the case of *in-situ* data processing with devices that have limited power and processing resources. Use of more robust methods in microcontroller-based environment, such as automatic differentiation²² and

finite element method,²³ may be challenging because of computational overhead and memory requirements.²⁴ Although satisfactory results with the first-order central difference method (Eq. (4)) were obtained in this paper, promising possibilities for future work by using the second-order central difference method, Richardson extrapolation, or smoothness correction technique can be seen.

In the third step, angular frequency ω_o at which dZ_s has the minimum was estimated:

$$\omega_o = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}R_2C_2}. \quad (5)$$

Solving the set of Eqs. (2), (3) and (5) led to the frequency-dependent set of solutions for model parameters ($R_1(\omega_i)$, $R_2(\omega_i)$ and $C_2(\omega_i)$):

$$R_1(\omega_i) = (2(dZ_s(i)\omega(i) \wedge 2 + 2Z_s(i)\omega(i) + 3dZ_s(i)\omega_o^2))/w(i) \wedge (1/2)/2, \quad (6)$$

$$R_2(\omega_i) = (\sqrt{6}(-dZ_s(i)\omega^3(i) - 3dZ_s(i)\omega(i)\omega_o^2 + 6Z_s(i)\omega_o^2) \wedge (1/2))/(6\omega_o) - (2dZ_s(i)\omega^2(i) + 4Z_s(i)\omega(i) + 6dZ_s(i)\omega_o^2) \wedge (1/2)/(2\sqrt{w(i)}), \quad (7)$$

$$C_2(\omega_i) = -(\sqrt{3\omega(i)\omega(i)}(\sqrt{2\omega_o}(dZ_s(i)\omega^2(i) + 2Z_s(i)\omega(i) + 3dZ_s(i)\omega_o^2) \wedge (1/2) + (\sqrt{6}\sqrt{\omega(i)}(-dZ_s(i)\omega^3(i) - 3dZ_s(i)\omega(i)\omega_o^2 + 6Z_s(i)\omega_o^2) \wedge (1/2))/3))/ \times (dZ_s(i)(\omega^2(i) + 3\omega_o^2) \wedge 2). \quad (8)$$

The final estimated values of R_1 , R_2 and C_2 were calculated as means of arrays obtained with Eqs. (6)–(8).

4. Results

4.1. Synthetic datasets

The proposed estimation method was initially validated using synthetic dataset and linear frequency distribution. Impedance modulus of the 2R-1C circuit ($R_1 = 0.47\text{ k}\Omega$, $R_2 = 1\text{ k}\Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.7\text{ nF}$) was calculated using the Eq. (1) at $N = 100$ points in the frequency range 1 kHz–100 kHz. A more realistic dataset was created by adding 0.05% of the random noise. Noise level, frequency range and number of the frequency points were chosen to meet the features of measurement hardware that will be used later on (Hioki IM3590). Hioki IM3590 is a chemical impedance analyzer, designed for applications in characterization electrochemical components and materials, batteries, etc.²⁵ Reference values of model parameters ($R_1 = 0.47\text{ k}\Omega$, $R_2 = 1\text{ k}\Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.7\text{ nF}$) were selected in compliance with the later experimental work.

Estimated values were: $R_1 = 446.95\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 1010.67\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.56\text{ nF}$. The average relative error in parameter estimation was lower than 3%. The comparison of reference and estimated values of impedance modulus is shown in Fig. 2(a). In the same figure, the numerical approximation of the dZ_s was plotted, as well as the characteristic frequency used for the parameter estimation (defined with Eq. (5)).

Fig. 2. Comparison of reference (red solid) and estimated (blue circles) values of impedance modulus in the case of synthetic datasets with (a) linear and (b) logarithmic frequency distribution with 0.25% random noise. The numerical approximation of the dZ_s is plotted with black line and squares (Color online).

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for impedance modulus was $8.35\ \Omega$, while the average relative errors on the complete set of frequencies was 0.89%.

The robustness of the proposed estimation method was analyzed by doubling the level of the measurement noise. Estimated values were: $R_1 = 445.24\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 1012.37\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.58\ \text{nF}$. Therefore, higher noise level slightly increased the average estimation error to 3.06%, and RMSE to $13.91\ \Omega$.

A similar estimation accuracy with the reduced number of frequency points can be achieved with logarithmic frequency distribution. For example, if noise level is 0.05% with $N = 32$, estimated values are: $R_1 = 460.27\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 1009.24\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.76\ \text{nF}$. The comparison of the reference and estimated values of impedance modulus is shown in Fig. 2(b). The RMSE for impedance modulus in this case was about 1.5 times higher ($12.88\ \Omega$), while the average relative errors on the complete set of frequencies were 0.99%, which is around 12.5% higher, when compared to the linear frequency step. Even though logarithmic frequency distribution with $N = 32$ resulted in slightly worse performances, it was achieved using only one third of the frequency points from dataset with linear frequency distribution.

Both synthetic datasets (with linear and logarithmic frequency distribution) are available in App. A of Supplementary Materials.

4.2. Experimentally obtained impedance of the 2R-1C circuit

For validation with experimentally obtained impedance of the 2R-1C circuit, discrete components with specified nominal values of $0.47\ \text{k}\Omega$, $1\ \text{k}\Omega$, and $4.70\ \text{nF}$ for R_1 , R_2 , and C_2 were used, respectively. The resistors utilized had a tolerance of 5%, while the capacitor's tolerance was 10%. To measure the impedance modulus, Hioki IM3590 device was employed. In addition to that, reference values of model parameters were obtained as the measurement average for each discrete component taken at the given frequency range: $R_1 = 467.12\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 985.34\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.85\ \text{nF}$.

Fig. 3. Comparison of reference (red solid) and estimated (blue circles) values of impedance modulus in the case of experimentally obtained impedance (Color online).

Estimated values were: $R_1 = 473.47\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 983.30\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 4.92\ \text{nF}$. The average relative errors in estimations of model parameters (R_1 , R_2 and C_2) were: 1.36%, 0.21% and 1.61%, respectively. Figure 3 illustrates the comparison between the reference values and the estimated values of the impedance modulus.

Appendix A of Supplementary Materials contains experimentally acquired impedance data.

4.3. Experimentally obtained impedance of tap water

EIS is widely utilized as a non-destructive method for evaluating the physicochemical characteristics of materials and liquids, including tap water.²⁶ We used the EIS dataset (frequency range from 10 mHz to 5 mHz) of tap water²⁷ provided by Zurich Instruments within the private communication. MFIA Impedance Analyzer with a pair of parallel (coated) metal plates (cell constant of 1 cm) was used. A photo of the actual measurement setup can be seen in Ref. 27. The Nyquist plot of measured values within the full frequency range is shown in Fig. 4(a). A much more complex equivalent circuit than 2R-1C is needed to adequately fit the EIS data in complete frequency range. For example, an addition of semi-empirical elements, such as constant phase elements and Warburg element might be needed. In initial stage of EIS analysis, it is common to cover range of frequencies as wide as possible, because it can help in understanding the complete electrochemical processes. However, in repeated estimation and *in-situ* monitoring, it is much more convenient to select one portion of the frequency range where four rules mentioned in Introduction are satisfied. With such an approach, it is possible to avoid low-frequency measurements that are slow (period of $f = 10\ \text{mHz}$ is 100 s) and processing the large number of datapoints.

Using the 21 points within the frequency range from 89.2 kHz to 668 kHz, shown as the inset of Fig. 4(a), and the proposed method, estimated values of model parameters were: $R_1 = 445.35\ \Omega$, $R_2 = 2223.28\ \Omega$ and $C_2 = 0.23\ \text{nF}$. The corresponding

Fig. 4. (a) The Nyquist plot of measured values, and (b) the comparison of the measured (red circles) and estimated (blue solid with crosses) impedance modulus (Color online).

RMSE for impedance modulus was $8.27\ \Omega$, while the average relative error between the measured and estimated impedance modulus was 0.37% . A comparison between the measured and estimated impedance is shown in Fig. 4(b).

4.4. Embedded hardware-based implementation

To perform parameter estimation, versatile microcontroller board Mega2560 (Fig. 5), utilizing the ATmega2560 chip, was employed in this work.

Appendix B (Supplementary Materials) of this paper includes the program code. Our program code was written in such a way that it uses serial communication for debugging purposes. EIS processing starts with self-multiplication of array that contains values of impedance modulus. The resulting array is further processed by finding the numerical approximation of the first derivative using the central difference method, and estimating the frequency at which the first derivative has the extremum. The value of such frequency is used for the estimation of model parameters, along with the arrays that contain multiplication result and the numerical

Fig. 5. Used Embedded Hardware (Mega2560 board).

approximation of the first derivative. Finally, model parameters values are extracted as means of arrays obtained in the previous step.

The impedance modulus is stored in the flash memory of the microcontroller. The program code itself occupies less than 2% of the total flash memory capacity (256 kB), leaving ample space for additional functionality. Furthermore, the global variables used by the program utilize less than 23% of the available SRAM (8 kB), ensuring efficient memory utilization.

The same results were achieved using our embedded hardware-based implementation as with MATLAB installed on the PC-based station. Noteworthy contributions of our embedded hardware-based implementation work are: (1) necessity of only the basic mathematical operations, (2) reliable data processing with the 4-byte floating point arithmetic, (3) the estimation time of 80 ms for 100 data-points deemed appropriate for various practical applications. For example, adding a few NaCl salt grains into the clean tap water resulted in noticeable change of impedance within 8 s.²⁷ Therefore, this method of estimation enables the observation of rapidly evolving electrochemical processes in the liquids.

5. Discussion

Presented results in Sec. 4 clearly indicated that the proposed system is capable of reliable parameter estimation of 2R-1C circuit for different number of points and frequency distributions (linear and logarithmic), as well as in the case of noise levels that are higher than those commonly used in electrochemical instrumentation. Moreover, it has been shown that processing of experimentally obtained impedance of 2R-1C circuit made from discrete components, as well as tap water EIS data, is possible. Notably, the proposed estimation method can be deployed on the microcontroller-based embedded hardware where just 80 ms is required for processing dataset with 100 points.

The formulation of the key performance indicators and comparison with the literature is based on multiple criteria, including the estimation accuracy, as well as the processing and memory resources required for the implementation. Lack of datasets in some published works by other authors prevents the direct comparison of our work with such approaches. However, our research group recently published three works where parameter estimation methods of 2R-1C circuit were presented.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Experimentally obtained impedance of the 2R-1C circuit described in 4.2 was used for the comparisons. Table 1 illustrates the accuracy comparison between the proposed method and the other three methods. The results demonstrate that among the four methods, the proposed method achieves the lowest average relative error (1.06%) in estimation. The total relative error (sum of errors for R_1 , R_2 and C_2) was 3.18%.

A comparative analysis was conducted between the proposed estimation method and the approaches presented in references^{14,15} and¹⁶ in terms of performances when deployed on the same embedded hardware platform (Mega2560). Main indicators

Table 1. Comparison of the proposed method with the relevant works from literature in terms of accuracy and use of resources.

Estimation method (reference)	Relative errors			Performance indicators		
	R_1	R_2	C_2	Estimation time (ms)	Flash usage (bytes)	SRAM usage (bytes)
Ref. 14	1.59%	0.24%	1.09%	34.02	4812	1145
Ref. 15	1.54%	0.21%	1.24%	34.09	6804	5003
Ref. 16	3.49%	2.24%	4.05%	106.01	5022	1142
This work	1.36%	0.21%	1.61%	80.56	6144	1945

Table 2. Comparison of the proposed method with the relevant works from the literature.

Reference, year	Limitation	Our contribution
Ref. 5, (2020)	Deployment on the PC-based hardware configurations and requirement for the specialized software packages (Zview) limits <i>in-situ</i> applications and continuous autonomous parameter estimation.	Our estimation method does not require PC-based processing units, or specific software, enabling <i>in-situ</i> estimation and the decision-making at the measurement spot.
Ref. 6, (2005) Ref. 7, (2021)	NLLS-based method requires good initial values for the first iteration, otherwise low estimation accuracy and a convergence to the local minimum can occur.	Our estimation method does not require initial values.
Ref. 8, 2017	(1) The selection of the global search characteristic of stochastic methods has impact on the performances. (2) Requires initial values.	Our estimation method is not dependent on any of the global search characteristics, and does not require initial values.
Ref. 9, (2013)	The algorithm may converge to a suboptimal solution before fully exploring the search space.	Our estimation method is not iterative and there is no possibility of converging to a suboptimal solution.
Ref. 14, (2023) Ref. 15, (2021) Ref. 16, (2022)	Requires the complex impedance as input.	Our estimation method uses only impedance modulus which reduces the size of input data, and also enables the elimination of the need for the phase detector.
Ref. 17, (2019)	Necessitates repetitive estimation of covariance and numerical minimization techniques, which are not well suited for real-time parameter estimation conducted <i>in-situ</i> .	Our estimation method does not rely on any numerical minimization techniques, enabling fast and reliable <i>in-situ</i> estimations.
Ref. 18, (2012)	(1) Requires predefining the duration of the square pulse and the value of the reference resistor. (2) There is no possibility to have direct comparison between measured and estimated values.	Our estimation method does not require any configuration before the estimation. It uses measured impedance modulus, and comparison between the estimation and measured values is possible.

were estimation time, usage of flash memory and SRAM usage. As shown in Table 1, the proposed estimation method is faster than¹⁶ and requires less flash memory, but higher amount of SRAM is occupied. On the other hand, the proposed method requires less flash memory and SRAM than,¹⁵ but it is slower. The proposed method has lower performance than,¹⁴ but it uses only impedance modulus, rather than real part of impedance,¹⁴ which requires more complex measurement circuit.

In addition to comparisons with our previous studies, it is also important to summarize the main contributions of our work when compared to other research groups (Table 2).

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces an innovative approach to extracting the values of the 2R-1C circuit elements. Improving the parameter estimation methodology for this circuit has practical implications in understanding and analyzing the electrical behavior of electrochemical systems. Unlike traditional methods, this technique is non-iterative and solely relies on the impedance modulus. Performed analysis with synthetic and experimentally obtained impedance showed that it is possible to have dependable parameter estimation with the proposed method. Processing dataset with one hundred floating point values of impedance modulus, as well as parameter estimation, is performed in just 80 ms using the embedded hardware platform based on the 8-bit microcontroller.

Overall, this work contributes to advancing the field of electrochemical modeling and analysis by providing a novel methodology that enhances automation, reduces user inputs, and enables *in-situ* parameter extraction.

7. Future Work

The 2R-1C equivalent circuit assumes linearity in the electrical behavior of electrochemical systems. However, many real-world systems exhibit nonlinear behavior. Future research will explore the incorporation of nonlinear elements (such as constant phase element) or models into the estimation method.

Further experimental validations in diverse electrochemical applications are also very interesting, with the goal of developing prototype for continuous monitoring of electrochemical systems and decision making.

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References

1. V. Vivier and M. E. Orazem, Impedance analysis of electrochemical systems, *Chem. Rev.* **122** (2022) 11131–11168.
2. J. E. B. Randles, Kinetics of rapid electrode reactions, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.* **1** (1947) 11–19.
3. S. Buller, M. Thele, R. W. De Doncker and E. Karden, Impedance-based simulation models of supercapacitors and Li-ion batteries for power electronic applications, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.* **41** (2005) 742–747.
4. A. M. Dhirde, N. V. Dale, H. Salehfar, M. D. Mann and T.-H. Han, Equivalent electric circuit modeling and performance analysis of a PEM fuel cell stack using impedance spectroscopy, *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.* **25** (2010) 778–786.
5. M. Qing, H. Liang, J. Zhang, H. E. Najafabadi, H. Zhan and H. Leung, Detection mechanism of water content in oil–water emulsions by coaxial double cylinder electrodes, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **70** (2020) 1–10.
6. H. Ozier-Lafontaine and T. Bajazet, Analysis of root growth by impedance spectroscopy (EIS), *Plant Soil* **277** (2005) 299–313.
7. Y. Wang, F. Huang, B. Pan, Y. Li and B. Liu, Augmented system model-based online collaborative determination of lead–acid battery states for energy management of vehicles, *Meas. Control* **54** (2021) 88–101.
8. M. A. Abud Kappel, F. C. Peixoto, G. M. Platt, R. P. Domingos and I. N. Bastos, A study of equivalent electrical circuit fitting to electrochemical impedance using a stochastic method, *Appl. Soft Comput.* **50** (2017) 183–193.
9. S. Sharifi-Asl, M. L. Taylor, Z. Lu, G. R. Engelhardt, B. Kursten and D. D. Macdonald, Modeling of the electrochemical impedance spectroscopic behavior of passive iron using a genetic algorithm approach, *Electrochim. Acta* **102** (2013) 161–173.
10. O. A. Arqub and Z. Abo-Hammour, Numerical solution of systems of second-order boundary value problems using continuous genetic algorithm, *Inf. Sci.* **279** (2014) 396–415.
11. Z. Abo-Hammour, O. Alsmadi, S. Momani and O. Abu Arqub, A genetic algorithm approach for prediction of linear dynamical systems, *Math. Prob. Eng.* **2013** (2013) 1–12.
12. Z. Abo-Hammour, O. Abu Arqub, S. Momani and N. Shawagfeh, Optimization solution of troesch’s and bratu’s problems of ordinary type using novel continuous genetic algorithm, *Discrete Dyn. Nat. Soc.* **2014** (2014) 1–15.
13. O. Abu Arqub, Z. Abo-Hammour, S. Momani and N. Shawagfeh, Solving singular two-point boundary value problems using continuous genetic algorithm, *Abstr. Appl. Anal.* **2012** (2012) 1–25.
14. M. Simić, A. K. Stavrakis, T. Kojić, V. Jeoti and G. M. Stojanović, Parameter estimation of the randles equivalent electrical circuit using only real part of the impedance, *IEEE Sens. J.* **23** (2023) 4922–4929.
15. M. Simić, A. K. Stavrakis and G. M. Stojanović, A low-complexity method for parameter estimation of the simplified randles circuit with experimental verification, *IEEE Sens. J.* **21** (2021) 24209–24217.

16. M. Simic, A. K. Stavrakis, V. Jeoti and G. M. Stojanovic, A randles circuit parameter estimation of Li-ion batteries with embedded hardware, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* **71** (2022) 1–12.
17. R. G. Ramírez-Chavarría, M. I. Müller, R. Mattila, G. Quintana-Carapia and C. Sánchez-Pérez, A framework for high-resolution frequency response measurement and parameter estimation in microscale impedance applications, *Measurement* **148** (2019) 106913.
18. Z. Czaja, A microcontroller system for measurement of three independent components in impedance sensors using a single square pulse, *Sens. Actuators A Phys.* **173** (2012) 284–292.
19. K. Vanchinathan and N. Selvagesan, Adaptive fractional order pid controller tuning for brushless dc motor using artificial bee colony algorithm, *Results Control Optim.* **4** (2021) 100032.
20. K. Vanchinathan, K. R. Valluvan, C. Gnanavel and C. Gokul, Numerical simulation and experimental verification of fractional-order π^λ controller for solar pv fed sensorless brushless dc motor using whale optimization algorithm, *Electr. Power Compon. Syst.* **50** (2022) 64–80.
21. V. Kumarasamy, V. K. Ramasamy and G. Chinnaraj, Systematic design of multi-objective enhanced genetic algorithm optimized fractional order PID controller for sensorless brushless DC motor drive, *CW* **48** (2022) 479–492.
22. P. Enciu, L. Gerbaud and F. Wurtz, Automatic differentiation applied for optimization of dynamical systems, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **46** (2010) 2943–2946.
23. A. Demenko and J. K. Sykulski, Analogies between finite-difference and finite-element methods for scalar and vector potential formulations in magnetic field calculations, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **52** (2016) 1–6.
24. A. Griewank and A. Walther, *Evaluating derivatives: Principles and techniques of algorithmic differentiation* (SIAM, 2008).
25. Hioki E.E. Corporation, Hioki IM3590, (2021).
26. R. Gruden and O. Kanoun, Water quality assessment by combining impedance spectroscopy measurement with cyclic voltammetry, *Proc. Sensor 2013* (AMA Service GmbH, Germany, Nürnberg, 2013), pp. 164–169.
27. M. Li, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy of tap water, <https://www.zhinst.com/europe/en/blogs/electrochemical-impedance-spectroscopy-tap-water> (2020).